

Evaluation of Earth Observation Embeddings for Aboveground Biomass Mapping across European Forests

Yu-Feng Ho^{1,3,*}, Leandro Parente¹, Qian Song², Lea Enguehard², Madlene Nussbaum³, Derek Karssenber³

¹ OpenGeoHub Foundation, Doorwerth, the Netherlands, yu-feng.ho@opengeohub.org, leandro.parente@opengeohub.org

² GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Helmholtz Association of National Research Centres, Potsdam, Germany, qian.song@gfz.de, lea.inguehard@gfz.de,

³ Faculty of Geoscience, Utrecht University, Utrecht, the Netherlands, m.nussbaum@uu.nl, d.karssenber@uu.nl

* corresponding author

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Abstract: Accurate estimation of aboveground biomass is critical for comprehensive forest monitoring. This study evaluates the predictive performance and uncertainty of two novel 10-m global time-series Earth Observation embeddings, TESSERA and Google Satellite Embedding (AlphaEarth), against a baseline of combined Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data. Reference biomass estimates were derived from National Forest Inventory (NFI) and airborne lidar scanning. To predict aboveground biomass (AGB) and quantify model uncertainty, we employed a Quantile Random Forest Regressor (QRFR). Additionally, we assessed the impact of integrating a global terrain height model (GEDTM) into the predictive feature space. Our results demonstrate that both the TESSERA and AlphaEarth embeddings achieve comparable accuracy to the traditional Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 baseline, measured by RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and ME. Furthermore, incorporating the GEDTM topographical features improved model accuracy and reduced overall prediction uncertainty, quantified by the Mean Prediction Interval (MPI). Notably, AlphaEarth did not benefit significantly from the addition of terrain variables, likely because its underlying architecture inherently captures these features from its training data. These findings validate the efficacy of global EO embeddings for high-resolution biomass mapping while highlighting that integrating additional features, such as topographical features, improves model performance.

Keywords: woody biomass; forest; machine learning; uncertainty.

1 Introduction

Aboveground biomass (AGB) and soil organic matter represent the primary mechanisms for carbon sequestration within the terrestrial carbon cycle (Carlson et al. 2001). Although the major carbon stock is located in sediments under the sea, plant growth and decay of terrestrial vegetation contribute a relatively huge portion of the carbon flux. Zooming into terrestrial vegetation, forest ecosystems store the majority of aboveground biomass globally (Post et al. 1990), where live biomass (above and below ground) has ~40 %, second to soil (to 1m depth) containing 44% in forest ecosystems (Sedjo et al. 1993). Estimation of forest aboveground biomass, especially woody biomass, is thus crucial for monitoring the carbon flux.

Earth observation (EO) specializes in covering large-scale high-resolution information and frequent revisiting. Combining multiple types of remote sensing data (LiDAR, SAR, optical) and ground-truth measurements by machine learning and deep learning algorithms enables to generate high-resolution, accurate, and spatially explicit AGB maps across various ecosystems, contributing significantly to carbon cycle understanding and sustainable forest management (Alvarez et al. 2024). Although using EO with machine learning can achieve higher detail AGB maps over large areas and more frequent timestamps, the complexity of applying EO for large areas remains significant technical challenges.

Foundational models (FM), or by extension EO embeddings have the potential to address these technical challenges. EO-FM is a transformative advancement for EO. It promises enhanced analysis and interpretation of complex spatial, spectral, and temporal data, by self-supervised learning from multisource EO input data (Ramachandran et al. 2025). EO embeddings leverage on the concept of EO-FM, but instead of delivering a model, it outputs high-dimensional numerical vectors that distill massive amounts of raw satellite imagery into compact, semantic representations of the Earth's surface. EO embeddings could not only reduce the burden of data preprocessing but also substantially compresses the data volume due to their self-supervised encoding (Klemmer et al. 2025). Fang et al. (2026) further indicate that combining EO embeddings with external layers can further improve the model performance. In relation to our research scope of AGB mapping, the current state-of-art EO embeddings from TESSERA and AlphaEarth have shown the competence for their downstream AGB mapping to reach similar accuracies as current state-of-art machine learning methods that trained on EO data (Brown et al. 2025, Feng et al. 2025). We are then interested in investigating EO embedding potential on AGB mapping, to evaluate if there is a tradeoff between EO embedding compression and data accuracy, and furthermore, if additional landscape attributes will improve AGB mapping, and which EO embedding setup remains higher accuracy and lower uncertainty in mapping European forests.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Input data

2.1.1 Reference AGB

The reference data in this study is derived from National Forest Inventories (NFIs) and is based on detailed AGB predictions at the local scale. We collected Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) data to match the location and survey year of each NFI in the Czech Republic, Italy, and the Netherlands. We applied allometric equations to diameter at breast height (DBH), species, and tree height to generate biomass estimates. Each ALS dataset has various spatial support from 50 centimeters to 5 meters. We resampled them into 10-m pixels using average aggregation to produce the homogeneous ALS-derived data. Afterward, we trained several models, such as linear regression, random forests, and geostatistical models using ALS-derived data and NFI data. Finally, we predicted aboveground biomass at 10-m resolution with the selected final model based on performance.

2.1.2 Covariates

For this research, we utilized the only two available 10-m global coverage time-series embeddings: TESSERA and Google Satellite Embedding (AlphaEarth) (Feng et al. 2025, Brown et al. 2025). TESSERA was acquired via its GitHub repository (TESSERA 2026). AlphaEarth was downloaded via Source Cooperative, hosted by Taylor Geospatial (AlphaEarth Foundations 2026). These data were downloaded in individual tiles, each retaining its specific UTM coordinate system. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data serve as fundamental layers for both biomass mapping and the generation of time-series EO embeddings. By modifying scripts from the TESSERA download pipeline, we retrieved partial raw scenes for both satellites. For Sentinel-1, we selected the Radiometric Terrain Corrected (RTC) product generated by the Observational Products for End-Users from Remote Sensing Analysis (OPERA) project (OPERA-RTC-S1). This 30m resolution product was downloaded from the ASF DAAC (NASA OPERA, n.d.a). Sentinel-2 data were similarly downloaded from the ASF DAAC (NASA OPERA, n.d.b) and the cloud pixels were masked by the associated Scene Classification Layer (SCL). Furthermore, because both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data are organized into discrete scenes that do not perfectly align with our reference grids, we mosaicked the layers and cropped them to match the reference tile boundaries. Furthermore, to account for the 5-day and 6-day revisit cycle of the Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data respectively, we temporally aggregated the time series to derive annual composite values. Specifically, we calculated the 10th percentile (p10), median, and 90th percentile (p90) for the available Sentinel data within the year. We also incorporated the first and only publicly available global terrain height model, along with its derivatives, at resolutions of 30m and coarser (30m, 60m, 120m, 240m, 480m, and 960m) - Global Ensemble Terrain Model (GEDTM) dataset, documented by Ho et al. (2025). To align with the reference AGB data, all terrain layers were resampled to a 10m resolution using cubic spline interpolation, reprojected to a common UTM coordinate

system and cropped to matching tile boundaries. This method was chosen to preserve spatial features and ensure smooth transitions in pixel values, which is beneficial for the subsequent machine learning processes.

2.2 Modeling and uncertainty quantification

To benchmark the performance of different EO embeddings and evaluate the benefits of additional features, we selected a single random forest regressor to establish a baseline. The random forest algorithm has proven its scalability for large-scale mapping, high-resolution data, and time-series space-time modeling (Hengl et al. 2026, Tian et al. 2025). We created spatial blocks within each test site by computing the semivariogram, using the sill value to define the block size. Afterwards, we took all the blocks and conducted an 80/20 random split of the blocks into a train and test set. The hyperparameter tuning was conducted within the train set by 5-fold cross-validation. The final models were trained with the train set and validated through the test site. Uncertainty quantification was conducted using an extended random forest implementation known as the Quantile Random Forest Regressor (QRFR). In practice, we adopted the function developed by Hengl et al. (2026). This modified function stores the full output distribution from each tree in the forest, allowing us to compute uncertainty based on confidence intervals using parametric or non-parametric statistical methods.

2.3 Accuracy Evaluation

In this study, we used four common metrics (Root Mean Square Error – RMSE, Mean Absolute Error – MAE, Mean Error – ME, R^2 for point estimate accuracy. For uncertainty assessment, we implemented Mean Prediction Interval (MPI) which is used to estimate the model confidence: A wider prediction interval indicates higher uncertainty in the estimates, whereas a narrower interval signifies lower uncertainty and greater precision (Kasraei et al. 2021). We employed Quantile Regression Forest (QRF) to estimate a conditional distribution ranging from the 5th to the 95th percentile at 5-unit increments. Based on these estimates, the MPI was calculated for prediction intervals (PI) ranging from 10% to 90%.

3 Results

The complete sample size is 220,702 points in 98 blocks across the three test sites (28, 24, and 46 blocks are in CZ, IT, and NL, respectively). The number of samples and blocks are equal in all the setups. TESSERA, AlphaEarth, and S1+S2 are represented by orange, blue, and green color pairs, respectively, within each pair, the lighter shade denotes the base model, while the darker shade indicates the inclusion of GEDTM. Incorporating GEDTM as a predictor drastically improves model accuracy across all configurations except AlphaEarth, where a slight improvement is observed. Furthermore, the TESSERA and AlphaEarth embeddings achieve comparable overall accuracy, measured by RMSE, MAE, R^2 , and ME, to the combined Sentinel-1/2 baseline. For the uncertainty assessment, Figure 2 illustrates the confidence level (CL)

Table 1. Evaluation of model performance across 6 covariate setups. Metrics include RMSE, MAE, R^2 , ME, MPI at a 90% threshold.

Setup	RMSE	MAE	ME	R-squared	MPI (CL:90%)
S1+S2	60.21	45.82	4.56	0.45	119.20
S1+S2+GEDTM	53.93	41.06	3.78	0.56	99.16
TESSERA	57.80	44.28	3.63	0.49	126.98
TESSERA+GEDTM	55.07	42.23	2.81	0.54	92.12
AlphaEarth	54.73	41.37	2.53	0.54	100.85
AlphaEarth+GEDTM	53.61	40.64	1.86	0.56	80.85

(%) against the MPI (in Mg/ha) across the different covariate setups. Notably, integrating the GEDTM features consistently reduces the MPI for the TESSERA, AlphaEarth, and Sentinel-1/2 models, indicating a clear reduction in overall prediction uncertainty. Table 1 summarizes the quantitative results for RMSE, MAE, R^2 , ME, MPI in 90% confidence level of 6 different covariate setups (Figure 1).

The reported RMSE, MAE, ME and MPI units are in Mg/ha. Finally, our results demonstrate that EO embeddings serve as a robust proxy for biomass mapping. Among the evaluated datasets, AlphaEarth proves to be the optimal configuration, its 64-band numerical vector representation provides a more effective alternative to the 128-band TESSERA embeddings. Consequently, AlphaEarth offers a more computationally feasible pathway for generating high-resolution (10-m) aboveground biomass products at a pan-European scale.

4 Discussion

Figure 1. Benchmark of 6 covariate setups impact on random forest model performance, quantified in RMSE, MAE, ME (in Mg/ha) and R^2 .

We establish that EO embeddings serve as a viable alternative to multispectral and SAR-based predictors. Our results suggest that adding terrain variables as predictors can improve the predictive accuracy of TESSERA. However, the performance gains for AlphaEarth remain marginal. This is likely because the AlphaEarth training dataset already incorporates GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) and DEM (Digital Elevation Model) data, allowing the model to inherently capture and apply these terrain features (Brown et al. 2025). Further research is

required to explore the internal mechanisms of this deep learning model and confirm this hypothesis. Conversely, we recommend that future iterations of TESSERA integrate terrain and climate data during training to enhance the embedding's versatility for various downstream modeling tasks. Nonetheless, the limitation of this research is obvious: only three sites of European forest were included.

Figure 2. MPI (Mg/ha) comparison of 6 covariate setups at CL: [10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, and 90], higher MPI at given CL shows the bigger range of prediction interval from the models.

Achieving a comprehensive representation of European forest ecosystems requires expanding the dataset to include all major biogeographical regions (Roekaerts et al. 2002), thereby improving the model's robustness at a continental scale.

5 Conclusions

The research concludes that EO embeddings when used as machine learning input result in a comparable predictive accuracy as using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 as input data. Secondly, it shows that the terrain height model and derivatives improve aboveground biomass prediction in European forests, but the improvement for AlphaEarth is insignificant. Nevertheless, the inclusion of terrain derivatives does reduce MPI for EO embeddings and Sentinel-1/2 based models. This research is limited by the few sites of European forests, the increase of aboveground biomass reference to cover different biogeographical regions can better represent the results of European forest.

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